

Problems and Prospect of Management of Archaeological Sites in West Bengal

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Abstract

Heritage Management is a global issue of the Twenty-first Century. It plays an important role in protection of archaeological remains and sites. There are number of legislations for protection of archaeological sites as well as artifacts in India. But most of the cases these legislations have been applied in historical sites and monuments. Few steps have been taken to protect the prehistoric sites and artifacts used or made by early human. Present study is an approach to explore the problems related to the protection of archaeological sites, prehistoric, proto historic as well as historic with a specific focus on West Bengal and India in general.

Key Words: heritage, management, legislations, public archaeology.

Introduction

In the course of Human evolution culture appeared as new kind of adaptation with non-genetic mode of inheritance. It is a unique possession of human kind and primarily restricted to the Genus Homo. It includes all of the capabilities and habits of man including norms and values, language, religious beliefs, laws, food procurement, rearing of children and other behaviour that are shared by a group. Culture is an adaptation in a specific environment. It is dynamic in nature and changes through time. The history of culture goes back to 2 million years ago and continued through generations. Anthropology deals with this cultural continuity from prehistoric to contemporary period to know the evolution and variation of culture through time and space. Archeological anthropology is a sub discipline of anthropology which is dealt with the both tangible aspects of prehistoric past when there is no written records and associated intangible aspects which are reconstructed through the analysis of prehistoric artifacts. Prehistoric culture gradually continued to proto-historic and historic period as well in contemporary period.

Sites preserve the relics of past human activities. It preserves both cultural remnants and fossil remains of early man. So it is very important to preserve the archeological sites as part of our cultural heritage, which has immense importance to know the past human behaviour and

important aspects of human bio-cultural evolution i.e. migration, cultural contact and socio-economic activities.

For the present study three sites have been taken into consideration one prehistoric site, one proto-historic site and an historical site in West Bengal to identify the problems of protection of the archaeological sites of West Bengal and alternative policies for preservation and protection of these cultural heritages.

A glimpse of heritage management

The word heritage includes urban centers, archaeological sites, industrial heritage, cultural landscape and heritage routes. The heritage of a country is its tradition that has been continued for many years and has been passed down from one generation to another.

As per the UNESCO declaration, the World Cultural and Natural Heritage have become an urgent issue globally since 1972. The concept of Cultural Resource Management was started with the beginning of the environment/conservational movement in the 1960s and 1970s. In 1970 the term "cultural resource management" was introduced by archaeologists as a parallel to Natural Resource Management. The primary objective was to preserve the tangible cultural heritage including Historic properties, older properties, museum collections, sites etc.

The Convention for Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage was adopted in the UNESCO Convention, 2003. The intangible heritage is consisted of traditional or indigenous knowledge, skills, oral history etc. (Jokilehto, 2005).

The literal evidences show that the Cultural Heritage Management was in action in India before the Colonial period. But there is no such terminology. The concept of preservation of heritage in India started since 1873, when Central Government issued a circular assigned to local Government regarding the preservation and caring of monuments which have historical and architectural value by Cunningham.

Interest in India's archaeological heritage was started by Sir William Jones since the foundation of the Asiatic Society in 1784. Alexander Cunningham, who is known as father of Indian archaeology also became interested in Indian archaeology and history during the colonial period. He started systematic investigation of archaeological heritage of India as early as 1848. He was pioneer in the countrywide survey of archaeological remains and was the first director of Archaeological Survey of India, which was started in 1861 (Roy, 1961).

Agents of destruction of archaeological sites

The heritage of prehistoric sites is very rich in India and has been destroyed day by day due to some unavoidable circumstances. The agents of destruction of categorized into two- natural agents and human agents. There are two types of human agents- incidental, which includes agriculture, land clearing, grazing, and construction of road, water management etc.

whereas intentional causes includes archaeological exploration and excavation, looting, vandalism. Natural agents are erosion of soil, deforestation and flood (Nickens, 1991)

Figure 1 Agents of destruction of archeological sites

Objectives

Archaeological sites have been destroyed day by day due to number of reasons. Objectives of the present study are to explore the causes of destruction of these sites and finding out the alternative ways to protect these rich cultural heritages.

Methodology

Data have been taken both from the primary and secondary sources. The secondary sources are existing literatures, books and reports whereas the primary data have been collected from the field. The methods which have been applied in the present field are survey and observation. Observation is an important tool to identify the nature of the sites, distribution of artifacts and the process of destruction.

An observation has been made on the different agencies responsible for destruction of the sites, such as deforestation, soil erosion, and displacement of the layer and riverine activities.

Local people were interviewed to gather information about the history of the site, present activities, their opinion and suggestion for protection of the site.

Studied sites

1. Site: Paruldanga in Birbhum district of West Bengal

Paruldanga (23°42' N and 87°43' E) is a Mesolithic site which was discovered in August 1979 and intensively explored by Prof. Subrata Chakrabarti during 1979 and 1994 (Chakrabarti 1998-1999).

Paruldanga is a village under the jurisdiction of Bolpur Police Station, Community Development Block Bolpur Sriniketan in Birbhum district of West Bengal. It is about 4 km from Santiniketan near the railway station Prantik. The soil is red lateritic and sandy in nature. Quartz nodules are also scattered on the site. The upper yellowish brown to reddish brown silt and yellowish silt deposition yielded Mesolithic tools.

Figure 2 Location of the site Paruldanga

(Source: <https://www.google.com/maps/search/paruldanga+/@23.6860649,87.6997616,718m/data>)

Present observation

A number of changes have been observed during the field work from 2009 to 2016. It was a bare land and highly erosion in nature. Due to soil erosion a number of tools have been dislocated from its original deposition due to rainfall. For expansion of habitation the trees were cut and soil became loosened which is one of the reasons of dislocating of archeological

materials. In recent years a number of mud houses built up in and around the site. They used to collect soil from the site to build their houses. Major destruction is done during the building of engineering college on the site and later construction of a helipad few years ago. The site is used as shortcut way and people crossed the site with two wheelers and van. Trucks also load clay from the site. So, the site is in danger due to both natural and manmade activities.

Figure 3 Threats observed in the site Paruladanga

2. Site: Mahisdal in Birbhum district of West Bengal

Mahisdal (23°42' N and 87°42' E) is an excavated chalcolithic site in west Bengal. It is also located under the jurisdiction of Bolpur Police Station, Community Development Block Bolpur Sriniketan in Birbhum district of West Bengal. It is situated in the northern bank of Kopai river and about 5 km. from Santiniketan. Shri R.P Das of the Eastern Circle of Archaeological Survey of India explored the area (IAR, 1962- 63) and later excavated the site in 1964 (IAR, 1963-64). The earliest C14 date of Mahisdal is 1380 BCE. The C-14 date of "Early Iron Age" period is Mahisdal is 690 CE (Chakrabarti *et. al*, 1993).

The site is in alluvium soil which is very fertile for agriculture. Present Mahisdal village is near to the site and the villagers primarily depend on agricultural produces from nearby fields of the ancient mound. The fertile soil and nearby water sources attracted the Chalcolithic people to live for a long periods of time.

The mound extends 230m. X 135 m. This yielded two phases of cultural deposits. Phase I is the chalcolithic which yielded ceramics of different types like red ware, brown ware, black and red ware, grey ware, black polished ware with fine texture. Different incised and pin holes

decorations are found in pot shards and white paintings have been noticed. These are parallel bonds, dots, triangle and geometric motifs. There is evidence of chalcolithic habitation with comprising floors of beaten earth with a soiling of rammed terracotta nodules and burnt husk impressed clay structure. Findings are also comprised of very small microliths mostly made on white chert, a flat copper celt with a convex cutting-edge, terracotta objects, bone tools, fragments of a decorated comb, bangles and a number of beads of semiprecious stones and steatite. A large quantity of charred rice has been found from the floor levels. Evidence of charred rice and burnt clay prove that the site perhaps was destroyed due to firing.

Period II yielded a large quantity of microliths, terracotta figurines and iron objects such as arrow-heads, spearheads, chisels and nails. The site was also used for procurement of iron as large quantity of iron ore and slags have been found. Clay sealing with two symbols and fragmentary terracotta figurines of an elephant in motion are interesting findings from the site. The faunal remains of include the jungle cat, pig, antlered deer, wolf and cattle (IAR, 1963-64).

Figure 4 location of the site Mahisdal

(Source:

<https://www.google.com/maps/place/Mahishdal,+West+Bengal+731204/@23.7123337,87.6914912,718m/data>)

Present observation

The mound is almost in destruction. One part of the mound is cut for agricultural purpose by the local villagers. The flat top of the northern part of the mound is used for play ground. The site is highly affected by the construction of Railway Bridge towards the eastern part of the

mound. The western part is steep in nature and erosion of soil has been noticed towards the agricultural field. The river Kopai is flowing from southern part of the mound and in rainy season a portion of the mound became water logged with the overflow of river. The Southern part the mound is used as cremation ground and gradually slopes towards the river. These activities both natural and manmade are the causes of destruction of archeological materials as well as the site Mahisdal.

Figure 5 Threats observed in the site Mahisdal

3. Site: Chandraketugarh in North twenty Four Parganas district of West Bengal

The site Chandraketugarh (Latitude 22⁰41'N and Longitude 88⁰42'E) is located near the township of Berachampa in Basirhat in North Twenty Four District of West Bengal. It is situated near Berachampa bus stoppage on the road to Haroa. It was an ancient port city by the side of the river Vidyadhari, which was connected with the river Ganga.

The site was first identified by a local doctor Tarak Nath Ghosh and brought to the attention of the then chief of Eastern circle of ASI, A. H. Longhurst in 1907. Later archaeologist Rakhaldas Banerji visited the site and made some publications on terracotta artifacts collected from the site. Asutosh Museum of Indian Art, University of Calcutta conducted a decade-long excavation on the site since 1956.

Chandraketugarh was the centre of civilization in coastal Bengal from 4th century BCE and the site was continuously occupied from pre- Mauryan times to the Sunga-Kushana period, Gupta and Pala dynasties in 12th century CE (Haque, 2001).

The site yielded huge terracotta objects including pottery, seals, rattles, toys, figurines and plaques. Period I (600 to 300 BCE) yielded NBPW, grey ware, punch marked coins, Period II (300 - 200 BCE) marked by the presence of terracotta objects, copper coins and stone beads. The Period III (200 BCE – 50 A.D.) yielded roulette wares and ceramic vases. Structural remains of temple were found during the Gupta period. Period IV belongs to the Kushan period (50 – 300 CE). Period V (300 - 500 CE) and VI (500 – 750 CE) belong to the post-Gupta age accompanied with huge terracotta object and habitation or temple structure known as Khana Mihirer Dhupi. It is located near the Berachampa bus stand. A fortification was found few km, away from the bus stand. These two places are of interest to the visitors. The site is protected by ASI.

Figure 6 Location of the site Chandraketugarh

(Source:

<https://www.google.com/maps/place/Chandraketugarh/@22.6975936,88.6809904,2892m/data>)

Present observation

Though the site is protected by ASI, a number of activities have been noticed related to the process of destruction of sites. The first site Khana Mihirer Dhupi is a gathering place of local

people. They gossip here on the ancient brick structure. Boys are climbing and jumping from the trees. The ancient water tank made of brick became a garbage dump. People make littering, throw polythene, burnt tobacco and broken wine bottles. Beside these human activities a number of natural destructions have been noticed like the deeply rooted trees and grasses on the brick structure.

In fortification area local people use the site for grazing of animals, drying of jute. People come here with two wheelers on the fortification and due to these activities ancient brick, terracotta and pot shards have been breaking into pieces. Sometimes the site is also used as picnic spot in winter. Firing, cooking and throwing of garbage are also destroying the site day by day. Some prohibitions regarding the protection of the site are in the signboards of ASI, but due to lack of awareness people do not obey these.

Beside these problems, a number of archeological materials yielded in different parts of the area are kept in personal collection. Sometimes the villagers also sell the objects which have archeological values. Recently a museum has been set up by the initiatives of the West Bengal Government.

Figure 7 Threats observed in the site Chandraketugarh

Summing up the problems

In India the archaeological sites which have been preserved by Archaeological Survey of India are mostly historic sites and monument, but the preservation of prehistoric sites is negligible. Most of the legislations are for preservation of monuments and antiquities. The prehistoric sites which provide valuable information about our past, have not been taken into consideration except a few cases.

A number of excavated sites are almost destroyed in West Bengal due to human agents including agriculture, cutting of soil, use of the land for playground and other development projects. Local people also are disobeyed the rules and regulation of the Government and sometimes engaged in different destruction activities. Most of the protected sites are now of an easy access to all, both men and animals. The sites sometimes were used for recreational activities.

The observation in the fieldwork in different parts of West Bengal reveals that local environment played an important role of the protection of archaeological sites. Vegetation cover and soil protect the sites and also artifacts. In humid condition taller plants prevent the direct rain splash on the soil by breaking the rain drops as in case of fortification in Chandraketurgarh. The fortification is full of tall trees. The vegetations which cover the top soil have been removed due to number of reasons like deforestation, field clearance, cutting of soil, animal grazing and agriculture. The shrubs covering most of the areas are burnt by local people for clearing the lands for agriculture and also for fuel consumption which results in loosening of the soil. Agriculture involves digging, hoeing and ploughing of soil which degenerates the archaeological materials and grazing of animals also loosen the top soil. These were noticed mostly in case of the site Mahisdal in Birbhum district of West Bengal.

The erosional activities dislocate and transport the artifacts. The archaeological remains are further redeposited in secondary location and lost its original identity in a particular geophysical condition. Gullies are formed along the edges of the boundary of a site due to cutting down the underlying soil at different depths due to the flow of water. Small gullies are sometimes close together joined and form a larger one. The direction of flow is towards the lower area from the higher elevated region. These types of destruction have been noticed in the sites Paruldanga and Mahisdal in Birbhum district of West Bengal.

Protective measures

Due to limitations of fund for protection of the sites, there is an alternative way i.e. increasing awareness programme, which is known as public archaeology. It deals with the role of the people for protection of archaeological sites. Increasing of awareness is an important tool of this approach. The people should be informed about the importance of the site and the artifacts found from the sites. Local people can play a vital role in the protection of the sites. They can be act as security and stop different intentional activities like exporting of archaeological materials, looting etc. the awareness camp should be arranged to aware local people about the importance of the site and values of the artifacts so that they can be act as a preserver of their own culture.

The artifacts collected from the different prehistoric sites are preserved and displays in the museums far away from the site. These artifacts should be preserved in site museum. Natural erosion can be minimized by proper planning and long-term management programme by putting a boundary around the site, fiber roofing. Above all a site Museum should be established to study the culture in proper landscape.

There are three stages of management of archaeological sites have been recommended (Fagan, 1991):

1. At first an overview of the cultural resources in an area with surroundings geophysical setting has to be planned. An ethnographic account also has to be prepared. Previous researches and culture history of the area also is an important aspect of the stage of research. On the basis of these potentialities of the sites an assessment of management procedures are recommended.
2. Then an archaeological assessment report should to be prepared including further assessment and re-exploration of known sites and surveying of new sites. This report is important for further developmental projects such as construction of building etc. This document is very useful for further research and to determine their eligibility for the National Register of Pre-historic and Historic sites and to establish suitable measures to protect them.
3. At final stage a management plan is proposed for protecting, preserving, interpreting and using cultural resources.

Conclusion

The discussions reveal that attention has not been given to the protection of the archeological sites. Both the state Government and the central Government should come forward to undertake different projects to protect our cultural heritage. There are number of constraints such as limitations of fund, politics and policies. In the present socio-political scenario, awareness programme has immense importance in the protection of archeological sites, artefacts and also minimization of intentional activities in an around the sites. So, the practice of public archaeology has an important role in protecting the rich cultural heritage of West Bengal as well as India and planned collaborative research would enhance the archeological tourism in future.

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